

ISIC-2022 International Scientific Interdisciplinary Conference

(odds ratio (OR) = 0.001 [95.0% confidence interval (CI) 0.001–0.105], $p = 0.021$); stage I and II hypertension (respectively, HR = 28.993 [95.0% CI 1.595–526.940], $p = 0.023$ and HR = 19.050 [95.0% CI 1.078–336.620], $p = 0.044$); the presence of left ventricular (LV) hypertrophy (LV = 3.169 [95.0% CI 1.103–3.108], $p = 0.032$); levels of very low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (VLDL-C) (OR = 49.032 [95.0% CI 4.155–578.644], $p = 0.022$); the presence of angina pectoris during significant exercise (OR = 6.199 [95.0% CI 1.129–34.039], $p = 0.036$).

These results indicated excessive compensatory activation of the β -adrenergic system, which provokes an increase in passive stiffness of the myocardium during the progression of heart failure (HF).

Conclusions: According to the obtained results, the comorbid course of coronary artery disease and T2DM is associated with a significant decrease in titin levels, which pathogenetically can be an early predictor of abnormalities in the morphology, contractile and dilatation function of the heart, and (as a result) the development of significant HF.

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**PRECLINICAL STUDY OF GASTROPROTECTIVE ACTION OF
CRYOPRESERVED PLACENTA EXTRACT**

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Treatment and prevention of peptic ulcer of the stomach is not only medical but also social problem. As a potential gastroprotective agent, our attention was drawn to the cryopreserved extract of placenta (CEP), because the literature convincingly demonstrated that this cryoextract eliminates the ulcerogenic action of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, which has a mechanism similar to peptic ulcer disease. The aim is to conduct a comparative assessment of the severity of antiulcer activity of CEP in prophylactic, therapeutic and therapeutic-prophylactic regimens for use in the model of ethanol-prednisolone gastric lesions.

Materials and methods of research. Studies were performed on laboratory male rats. To simulate damage to the gastric mucosa, rats were administered a single ethanol-prednisolone mixture: prednisolone (20 mg/kg) dissolved in 80.0% ethyl alcohol. In 24 h after administration of ethanol-prednisolone mixture, rats were removed from the experiment. CEP was used in three modes of administration: prophylactic – 1 time per day for 5 days before the administration of ethanol-prednisolone mixture; therapeutic – once in 60 minutes after administration of ethanol-prednisolone mixture; therapeutic and prophylactic – 1 time per for 3 days before the administration of ethanol-prednisolone mixture and 60 minutes after the administration of ethanol-prednisolone mixture. The effect of the studied drugs on the condition of the gastric mucosa was assessed macroscopically on a scale Yakovleva L.V.

Results. Macroscopic evaluation of the condition of the gastric mucosa showed that after 24 hours. after administration of the ethanol-prednisolone mixture, the degree of damage averaged 3.7 ± 0.37 points out of the five maximum possible points, and the ulcer index was 3.9 units from prophylactic five-day administration of esomeprazole resulted in an antiulcer activity of 45.9%, which was 1.8 times lower than that of the CEP. Erosive-ulcerative lesions of the gastric mucosa on the background of treatment-and-prophylactic modes of CEP were observed in only 28.6% of rats, which corresponded to the value of the ulcer index (0.3 units), and antiulcer activity was 92.3%. Under this regimen, the antiulcer activity of the CEP was practically comparable to the severity of the indicated activity of esomeprazole (97.4%).

Conclusions. The administration of CEP in the treatment mode (1 time after ethanol-prednisolone mixture) is accompanied by the lowest antiulcer activity, which was 22.2%, which was 4.1 times lower than the effectiveness of esomeprazole. Therapeutic and prophylactic use of CEP led to a statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) attenuation of the damaging effects of ethanol-predniolone mixture, and antiulcer activity was 92.3%, respectively.

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